

Supplementary Material to Paper: Discovery and Simulation of Data-Aware Business Processes

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Abstract—This document contains supplementary materials to the paper: “Discovery and Simulation of Data-Aware Business Processes,” presented at the 6th International Conference on Process Mining, October 14-18, 2024.

I. EVALUATION OVERVIEW

In the evaluation to define the data pattern generators for attributes in the synthetic evaluation, we explore two primary scenarios: (S), where a single activity modifies the attribute, and (M), where all activities within the process modify the attribute.

- **(S) Single Activity Modification:** In this scenario, only one specific activity can modify the attribute value. The attribute’s value is updated exclusively when this activity occurs, following the logic defined by the generator (e.g., linear increment).
- **(M) All Activities Modification:** Here, every activity in the process modifies the attribute value. Each event (activity) leads to an update in the attribute, which can result in a more complex sequence of changes.

These scenarios are applied under both event and global attribute contexts to examine how attributes are updated and propagated across cases and events. In the **Event Attributes** setting, attribute updates are localized to individual cases. The changes made by activities in one case do not affect the attribute values in other cases. Each case operates independently, and attribute values reset with each new case. In the **Global Attributes** setting, attribute updates accumulate across all cases. The changes made by activities in any case influence the attribute values in subsequent cases. The attribute values are carried over from one case to another, reflecting the cumulative nature of global attributes.

For example, consider a simple linear function generator that adds 1 to the previous value each time the attribute is updated, $x_i = x_{i-1} + 1$, with $x_0 = 0$. Consider a simple log with three consecutive cases (1, 2, and 3) that do not intersect in time, each consisting of three activity instances (a, b, and c). The logs will be presented in the format $\langle \text{activity}, \text{data_value} \rangle$, where “activity” is the activity label and *data_value* is the attribute value after the activity has been executed. Then, we can obtain the following versions

of the event log, considering a linear modification made by activity b (single activity modification) or by all the activities (multiple activities modification):

- **Single Activity, Event Attribute Setting (SE):**
 - Case 1: $\langle a, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 1 \rangle, \langle c, 1 \rangle$
 - Case 2: $\langle a, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 1 \rangle, \langle c, 1 \rangle$
 - Case 3: $\langle a, 0 \rangle, \langle c, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 1 \rangle$
- **Multiple Activities, Event Attribute Setting (ME):**
 - Case 1: $\langle a, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 2 \rangle, \langle c, 3 \rangle$
 - Case 2: $\langle a, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 2 \rangle, \langle c, 3 \rangle$
 - Case 3: $\langle a, 1 \rangle, \langle c, 2 \rangle, \langle b, 3 \rangle$
- **Single Activity, Global Attribute Setting (SG):**
 - Case 1: $\langle a, 0 \rangle, \langle b, 1 \rangle, \langle c, 1 \rangle$
 - Case 2: $\langle a, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 2 \rangle, \langle c, 2 \rangle$
 - Case 3: $\langle a, 2 \rangle, \langle c, 2 \rangle, \langle b, 3 \rangle$
- **Multiple Activities, Global Attribute Setting (MG):**
 - Case 1: $\langle a, 1 \rangle, \langle b, 2 \rangle, \langle c, 3 \rangle$
 - Case 2: $\langle a, 4 \rangle, \langle b, 5 \rangle, \langle c, 6 \rangle$
 - Case 3: $\langle a, 7 \rangle, \langle c, 8 \rangle, \langle b, 9 \rangle$

For simplicity, we omitted other attributes like resources and timestamps because we assume all the activities and cases are executed in sequence without any time interval intersections.

When generating the synthetic logs, the four cases previously described are applied for each of the following data generator patterns, grouped into two categories: numeric or continuous (Section II) and categorical (Section III).

II. NUMERIC (CONTINUOUS) DATA PATTERNS

Numeric (continuous) data patterns represent sequences of values that vary within a continuous range, capturing real-world phenomena such as economic growth, temperature changes, or production output. These patterns are useful for modeling processes that involve gradual changes over time or in response to certain conditions. Common numeric patterns include linear trends, exponential growth, sinusoidal sequences, and autoregressive models, each of which captures specific types of behavior in the data [1]. For instance, linear trends are used to model consistent, incremental changes, while exponential growth patterns are applied in scenarios like population growth or compound interest, where changes accelerate over time.

1) **Linear Trend Generator (LT), Fig. 1:** This function simulates data that follows a linear trend over time, where each value is a linear transformation of the previous value with some added randomness (noise). Linear trends are common in time series data, such as stock prices, sales figures, or temperature records over time [2].

Fig. 1: Linear Trend.

2) **Exponential Growth Generator (EG), Fig. 2:** This function generates data that follows an exponential growth pattern, where values increase rapidly at a constant growth rate, with some added noise. Exponential growth is often observed in population growth, compound interest in finance, and the spread of diseases [3].

Fig. 2: Exponential Growth.

3) **Lognormal Data Sequence Generator (LN), Fig. 3:** This function creates data following a lognormal distribution, modeled by the exponential growth of a normally distributed variable, with added noise. Lognormal distributions are common in financial modeling, income distributions, and biological measurements [4].

Fig. 3: Lognormal Data.

4) **AR(1) Sequence Generator (AR1), Fig. 4:** This function creates data based on an autoregressive model of order 1 (AR(1)), where each value depends on the previous value and

some noise. AR(1) models are used in financial time series, weather forecasting, and signal processing [1].

Fig. 4: AR(1) Sequence.

5) **Conditional Exponential Sequence Generator (CE), Fig. 5:** This function generates data following an exponential growth model, with growth rates changing at specified points, and includes noise. Conditional exponential models are used in modeling processes with phases of different growth rates, such as certain economic or biological processes [5].

Fig. 5: Conditional Exponential Growth.

6) **Periodic (Sinusoidal) Oscillations Generator (SS), Fig. 6:** This function produces data that follows a sinusoidal pattern, resembling waves with peaks and troughs, and includes some noise. Sinusoidal patterns are seen in seasonal data, sound waves, and alternating current (AC) electricity [6].

Fig. 6: Periodic (Sinusoidal) Oscillations.

7) **Switching Regression Sequence Generator (SR), Fig. 7:** This function produces data following a switching regression model, where different data segments follow different linear regressions with added noise. Switching regression models are used when different regimes or conditions, such as economic periods, affect the data [5].

Fig. 7: Switching Regression Sequence.

8) Piecewise Linear Sequence Generator (PL), Fig. 8:

This function generates data that follows a piecewise linear pattern, where the sequence is divided into segments with different linear trends and includes noise. Piecewise linear models are used in analyzing segmented trends in time series data, such as economic data with different phases [7].

Fig. 8: Piecewise Linear Sequence.

9) Uniform Data Sequence Generator (UD), Fig. 9:

This function generates data uniformly distributed within specified bounds, with some added noise. Uniform distributions are used in simulations, random sampling, and scenarios where each outcome within a range is equally likely [8].

Fig. 9: Random Generator from Uniform Distribution.

10) Normal Distribution Generator (ND), Fig. 10:

This function produces data based on a normal distribution, also known as a Gaussian distribution, with added noise. Normal distributions are ubiquitous in natural and social sciences, representing distributions of heights, test scores, and measurement errors [9].

To emulate real scenarios, each generated data value was perturbed with different levels of Gaussian noise. These ten continuous generators, each applied over the four setups of global/event and single/multiple updates, resulted in 40 distinct datasets.

Fig. 10: Random Generator from Normal Distribution.

III. CATEGORICAL (DISCRETE) DATA PATTERNS

The evaluation follows two main approaches to generating categorical data: modeling state transitions and generating random sequences. Each approach simulates different real-world phenomena and has distinct characteristics.

State transitions involve a Markov chain framework where a transition matrix defines the probability of transitioning from one state to another. Each state has specific probabilities of moving to other states (including possibly remaining in the same state). This approach captures the dependencies between consecutive states, reflecting how certain conditions or states influence subsequent ones [10]. Because the transitions depend on the current state, the sequence has a certain level of predictability, especially when probabilities are strongly biased (e.g., high self-transition). This approach is useful for modeling processes where the current state influences the next state. Examples include customer behavior modeling (where past actions affect future decisions) or system states in manufacturing processes.

Random State Sequences involves selecting states based on predefined probabilities without considering the previous state. This approach treats each state selection as independent of prior selections, focusing purely on the likelihood of each state appearing [10]. Because each state is selected independently, there is no inherent predictability based on the sequence. Each state stands alone, determined only by the predefined probabilities. This approach is suitable for scenarios where outcomes are independent, such as random draws in lotteries, simulation of random events, or simple probabilistic modeling where the past state does not influence future states.

1) **High Self-Transition (HST):** This pattern models a scenario where a state has a high probability of remaining the same when transitioning from one event to the next. For example, if a system is in a particular state (e.g., State 1), there is a high probability of staying in State 1 rather than transitioning to a different state. For example, consider three states: Idle, Active, and Paused. If the system is in the Active state, there is a 90% chance that it will remain Active during the next event and only a 10% chance that it will transition to another state.

2) **Uniform Exclusive Transitions (UET):** In this pattern, each state has an equal probability of transitioning to any of the other states, except for the current state. This means that no state can transition back to itself. For example, suppose there are three states: Start, Accept, and Reject. If the

system is in the *Start* state, it has an equal probability of transitioning to *Accept* or *Reject* but cannot remain in the *Start* state.

3) **Uniform Inclusive Transitions (UIT)**: Here, each state has an equal probability of transitioning to any other state, including itself. This pattern simulates a scenario where every state transition is equally likely. For example, for the same states *Start*, *Accept*, and *Reject*, the system has an equal probability of staying in *Start* or moving to *Accept* or *Reject* during each transition.

4) **Rare State Transition (RST)**: This pattern models transitions where a specific state is rarely entered. Most transitions lead to other states, but there is a low probability that the system will move to this rare state. For example, consider states *A*, *B*, and *C*, where *C* is rarely reached. The system might transition from *A* to *B* or from *B* to *A* frequently, but the transition to *C* happens only 5% of the cases.

5) **One-State Dominating Transitions (SDT)**: In this pattern, one particular state has a significantly higher probability of being transitioned to, regardless of the current state. This makes the dominating state a central node in the transition network. For example, consider states *A*, *B*, and *C*, where *C* is the dominating state. From either *A* or *B*, there is a much higher probability that the system will transition to *C* (e.g., 90%) than other transitions (e.g., with 5% to *A* or *B*).

6) **Cyclic Transitions (CT)**: This pattern involves states transitioning in a cyclic order. The system moves from one state to another in a loop, following a predetermined sequence. For example, for states *State 1*, *State 2*, *State 3*, and *State 4*, there is a high probability of the system transitioning from *State 1* to *State 2*, then to *State 3*, then to *State 4*, and finally back to *State 1*, repeating this cycle. Indeed, there is also a low probability of each state transitioning outside the expected cyclical pattern at each transition.

7) **Random States with Two Equal Probabilities (E2P)**: This pattern generates a sequence of (even) random states where two states have equal probabilities of being selected at each transition. This simulates a scenario where the outcome is binary and unbiased. For example, consider a process with two possible states: *On* and *Off*. There is an equal 50% chance of the system being in either *On* or *Off*, without considering the current state.

8) **Random States with Two Non-Equal Probabilities (N2P)**: In this pattern, two states are still possible, but they have different probabilities. This models a biased binary process where one state is more likely than the other. For example, consider states *Pass* and *Fail*. The system might have a 65% chance of transitioning to *Pass* and a 45% chance of transitioning to *Fail*, no matter the current state.

9) **Random States with Five Equal Probabilities (E5P)**: This pattern models a scenario with five possible states, each with an equal probability of being selected at each transition. This simulates a system with multiple, odd number of equally likely outcomes. For example, suppose there are five weather conditions: *Sunny*, *Cloudy*, *Rainy*, *Windy*, and *Snowy*.

Each condition has an equal 20% chance of being the system's state at any given time.

10) **Random States with Five Non-Equal Probabilities (N5P)**: This pattern involves five states with varying probabilities of being selected. Some states are more likely than others, reflecting a scenario with multiple outcomes where some are more common. For example, consider five customer satisfaction levels: *Very Unsatisfied*, *Unsatisfied*, *Neutral*, *Satisfied*, and *Very Satisfied*. The system might have probabilities of 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%, respectively, for transitioning to each state.

These ten categorical generators, each applied over the four setups of global/event and single/multiple updates, resulted in 40 distinct datasets.

IV. CASE ATTRIBUTE GENERATORS

Case attributes are created and scoped locally to each process instance (or case) and remain constant throughout the execution of that case. These attributes define characteristics of the case, such as the initial conditions, settings, or parameters that do not change as the process progresses through various activities in each case.

For example, assuming the same linear function that increases by one the attribute, $x_i = x_{i-1} + 1$, with $x_0 = 0$, used to illustrate global and event attributes before, would lead to the following values when applied in the context of case attributes:

- Case 1: $\langle a, 1 \rangle$, $\langle b, 1 \rangle$, $\langle c, 1 \rangle$
- Case 2: $\langle a, 2 \rangle$, $\langle b, 2 \rangle$, $\langle c, 2 \rangle$
- Case 3: $\langle a, 3 \rangle$, $\langle c, 3 \rangle$, $\langle b, 3 \rangle$

Although some of the generators used for case attributes—such as those based on normal, uniform, and exponential distributions—are similar to those applied to global and event attributes, their role and applications differ. In the context of global and event attributes, these generators create values that can change over time or across events, capturing dynamic or cumulative behaviors. However, when used for case attributes, these same generators serve a different purpose: they generate a single, consistent value that defines the entire case, i.e., they are created at the beginning of the corresponding process case and remain unaltered across the entire process execution. In other words, all the events in each case share the same case attribute value.

1) Case Attributes Following Continuous Distributions:

- **Fixed Value**: This pattern involves assigning a constant value to all the case attributes throughout the entire process. It is the simplest pattern and serves as a baseline for comparison with more complex patterns. Fixed values are often used when a particular attribute remains constant across different cases, such as a fixed discount rate or a standardized shipping fee.
- **Exponential Distribution**: Generates a single value for each case following an exponential distribution, providing a stable attribute that characterizes the case. While similar to Section II 2), here, the value remains unchanged within the case.

- **Uniform Distribution:** Produces a value for each case selected from a uniform distribution across a specified range. Again, while similar to Section II 9), this value remains unchanged within the case.
- **Normal Distribution:** Generates a single, fixed value for each case based on a normal distribution. This is similar to Section II 10), but it remains constant for each case in which it was generated.

2) Categorical Data Patterns:

- **2-State Equal Probabilities:** Assigns one of two possible states to each case with equal probability. Similar to Section III 7), here it remains constant for all the events within the corresponding case.
- **2-State Non-Equal Probabilities:** Assigns one of two possible states to each case but with non-equal probabilities. Similar to Section III 8), here it remains constant for all the events within the corresponding case.
- **5-State Equal Probabilities:** Assigns one of five possible states to each case with equal probability. Similar to Section III 9), here it remains constant for all the events within the corresponding case.
- **5-State Non-Equal Probabilities:** Assigns one of five possible states to each case but with non-equal probabilities. Similar to Section III 10), here it remains constant for all the events within the corresponding case.
- **10-State Equal Probabilities:** A new pattern that assigns one of ten possible states to each case, with each state having an equal chance of being selected. This can be used to model processes with a wide variety of equally likely outcomes, such as product options or service levels.
- **10-State Non-Equal Probabilities:** Similar to the 10-state equal probability pattern but with varying likelihoods for each state. This is useful for modeling complex scenarios where certain outcomes are more probable, reflecting real-world cases like customer segmentation or product selection.

We used 10 data patterns because case attributes are more straightforward to discover than event and global attributes. Reusing these generators for case attributes allows the same underlying statistical models to be applied in different contexts. The key difference lies in how the generated data is used: I) **global attributes** reflect shared or cumulative characteristics across all cases, II) **event attributes** capture dynamic changes within a case over time and III) **case attributes** provide a single value that remains constant throughout the process instance.

V. CONDITIONAL GATEWAYS EVALUATION

Branching conditions influence the sequence and order of activities within a process, therefore their evaluation targets their impact on the control flow dimension. To do this, we compared two different process simulation models: a data-unaware simulation model (NDAS) and our proposed data-aware simulation model (DAS).

We selected the data-unaware simulation model (NDAS) from [11] as our baseline for several practical reasons. The

NDAS model is structurally identical to our data-aware simulation model (DAS) in all non-data components, such as control flow, resource allocation, congestion, and time. The main difference lies in the absence of a data component in NDAS, where gateway decisions are based on probabilistic branching derived from historical frequency analysis, while DAS uses data-driven branching conditions related to specific data attributes. This selection ensures that any observed differences during the evaluation can be attributed primarily to the data component. Choosing a different baseline following different approaches in other dimensions, such as resource management or control flow, would have made it difficult to isolate the impact of the data component, i.e., improvements or issues could come from other factors rather than the integration of data-aware decision-making. Additionally, previous studies have shown that the differentiated (resources) model presented in [11] leads to more accurate simulation results than other non-differentiated (pooled resources) models. Therefore, it is a suitable baseline compared to previous existing works that rely mainly on undifferentiated models.

For the comparison, we designed a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) model with three sequential blocks, each consisting of a single activity, followed by a split gateway with five outgoing branches, and concluded with a join gateway (see Figure 11). We created two variants of this BPMN model to test different gateway behaviors: inclusive (OR) gateways and exclusive (XOR) gateways. The OR gateways allow multiple paths, while the XOR gateways restrict the flow to a single path.

Figure 11 illustrates the variant with OR gateways; the XOR version is identical except for the type of gateways used. Here, the gateway type, OR or XOR, impacts the number of execution paths. With OR gateways, each of the three split gateways can generate up to 31 ($2^5 - 1$) branch combinations, leading to 29 791 ($31 \times 31 \times 31$) possible execution paths, i.e., allowing multiple parallel activities. In contrast, XOR gateways are more restrictive, allowing only one branch per gateway, resulting in 125 possible execution paths. Therefore, OR gateways offer greater parallelism and complexity, while XOR gateways enforce a more linear and controlled flow.

We enhanced the control-flow mode in Figure 11 with simulation parameters. Specifically, to isolate the control flow's effects and avoid non-data-related waiting times, we allocated 100 full-day resources uniformly across the process. This allocation ensured that resource availability did not influence the process execution, allowing us to focus exclusively on the branching decisions. Additionally, we assigned random distribution functions to each activity's processing times to introduce variability and more accurately simulate real-world scenarios. Then, we generated 60 simulated event logs using PROSIMOS by adding the different branching conditions to assess later how both approaches NDAS and DAS perform on re-discovering them, specifically by re-simulating the re-discovered models and assessing how close the re-simulated logs were in terms of control flow from those 60 (synthetic) event logs used to re-discover the simulation model.

Fig. 11: BPMN model used to assess branching conditions (OR version).

1) **XOR (Exclusive) Gateway Conditions:** We used a set of 20 distinct datasets to evaluate how different attribute patterns influence XOR conditions in process simulations. Each dataset was generated using specific cases that modeled various categorical and continuous attribute patterns:

- **Equal Probability (EQ) Patterns** Each gateway is associated with a categorical attribute X . Incoming activities to a gateway, i.e., A, B, and C, randomly generate one of five discrete attribute values with equal probability. Then, each of the five outgoing flows from the **XOR** gateway should match one of these values, e.g., $Flow_1$ is triggered if $X == V1$, $Flow_2$ for $X == V2$, etc.
- **Random Probability (RD) Patterns** Each gateway is associated with a categorical attribute X . Incoming activities to a gateway, i.e., A, B, and C, randomly generate one of five discrete attribute values with different probabilities, e.g., $V1$ with 25%, $V2$ with 10%, $V3$ with 20%, $V4$ with 15%, $V5$ with 30%. Then, each of the five outgoing flows from the **XOR** gateway should match one of these values, e.g., $Flow_1$ if $X == V1$, $Flow_2$ if $X == V2$, etc.
- **Unbalanced (UB) Patterns:** Incoming activities to gateways only generate a single attribute value with 100% probability (e.g., always $V1$), even though conditions for the other values ($V2, V3, V4, V5$) remain defined and associated to an outgoing arc on each split gateway. Thus, it creates an unbalanced scenario where a single condition dominates at each gateway.
- **Continuous Normal Distribution (ND):** Incoming activities generate one floating number between 0 and 100 following a normal distribution assigned to an attribute X . Then, each outgoing flow in a gateway corresponds to a specific sub-range of 20 units (e.g., execute $Flow_1$ If $X \in [0, 20]$, $Flow_2$ If $X \in (20, 40]$, etc.). So, each flow's condition would assess **True** if the attribute value falls within the assigned range, such as $X \in [0, 20]$.
- **Continuous Exponential Distribution (ED):** Similar to the previously described **ND**, but with the attribute values generated following an exponential distribution.
- **Simple OR (\vee) Condition (CC1):** Involves a straightforward condition, including an OR (\vee) operator including categorical and numeric attributes. Each condition is evaluated independently, and if any of the conditions are **True**, the overall expression is satisfied. For example, $X_1 \in [0, 20] \vee X_2 = V1$.
- **Single AND (\wedge) Condition (CC2):** Involves a simple condition, including an AND (\wedge) operator including numeric attributes. All conditions must be **True** to satisfy the overall expression. For example, $X_1 > 0 \wedge X_2 \leq 20$.
- **Compound OR (\vee) Condition with Mixed Attribute Types (CC3):** Combines OR conditions involving continuous and discrete attributes. The OR (\vee) operator is used to evaluate whether any mixed criteria are satisfied. For example, $X_1 \in [0, 20] \vee X_2 = V1 \vee X_3 \in [21, 40]$.
- **Compound AND (\wedge) Condition with Mixed Attribute Types (CC4):** Combines conditions with the AND (\wedge) operator involving continuous and discrete attributes. All conditions, which may include a range check with $>$ and \leq operators and a specific discrete value, must be **True**. For example, $X_1 > 0 \wedge X_1 \leq 20 \wedge X_2 = V1$.
- **Nested OR (\vee) and AND (\wedge) Conditions (CC5):** Combining AND and OR operators, creating a nested structure. The expression may have multiple AND conditions within an OR block or vice versa. For example, $(X_1 \in [0, 20] \wedge X_2 = V1) \vee (X_1 \in [21, 40] \wedge X_2 = V2)$.

Note that in the case of complex conditions, **CC1-CC5**, attribute values are generated by the incoming activities that precede the corresponding gateway. Each condition pattern was also evaluated with an additional 20% noise perturbation, resulting in 20 datasets: 10 without noise (pure) and 10 with noise introduced in the data attribute generation. These patterns were applied twice—once assuming that attributes were modified by the activities leading up to the gateways (event attributes) and once assuming that attribute values were generated at the start of each case and remained constant throughout the case (case attributes). This approach led to 40 datasets: 20 under event attribute modification and 20 assuming case attributes.

2) **OR (Inclusive) Gateway Conditions:** Unlike XOR gateways, where only one outgoing flow can be selected, OR gateways allow multiple paths to be taken simultaneously, depending on the conditions. Therefore, the synthetic evaluation of OR gateways involved generating event logs based on different data patterns, adapted to allow the activation of multiple outgoing arcs due to conditions being fulfilled simultaneously.

Specifically, we applied the same data patterns used for XOR gateways—namely, equal probability (**EQ**), unbalanced probability (**UB**), normal distribution (**ND**), exponential distribution (**ED**), and complex conditions (**CC1**)—but with modifications to allow the activation of multiple outgoing arcs. For each of those five data patterns, we generated conditions to activate 1, 2, and 5 random outgoing flow arcs, capturing different levels of concurrency within the OR gateways as follows:

- **Single Flow Activation (F1):** In this scenario, the conditions were set up so that only one of the five possible outgoing flows could be activated due to a single condition evaluating `True`. Thus, similar to XOR gateways, each flow had a specific condition for discrete attributes like $X = V1$ for the first flow arc, $X = V2$ for the second, and so on. For continuous attributes, ranges were defined with no overlaps, e.g., $[0, 20]$ for the first flow arc, $(20, 40]$ for the second, etc., ensuring that only one flow could be activated at any given time.
- **Two Flow Activations (F2):** To ensure that two outgoing flow arcs from an OR gateway are activated simultaneously, the conditions for each arc are grouped and designed to allow concurrent activation within each pair. For discrete attributes, this is achieved by associating each pair of flow arcs with a combined condition using the logical “OR” operator (\vee). For example, if two arcs are paired, one might be initially associated with the condition $X = V1$ and the other with $X = V2$. The combined condition for these paired flow arcs would be $X = V1 \vee X = V2$, ensuring that if X takes either value $V1$ or $V2$, both arcs are activated simultaneously. The conditions are grouped similarly for continuous attributes by overlapping their value ranges. For example, if one flow arc in the pair is triggered by the condition $X \in [0, 30]$ and the other by $X \in [21, 50]$, the overlapping range $[21, 30]$ guarantees that when X falls within this interval, both flow arcs in the pair are activated.
- **Five Flow Activations (F5):** This scenario represents the most complex case, where the conditions are configured to ensure that all five outgoing flows from an OR gateway can be activated simultaneously. For discrete attributes, this is achieved by combining the conditions for all possible attribute values using the logical “OR” operator (\vee). Specifically, the condition is constructed as $X = V1 \vee X = V2 \vee X = V3 \vee X = V4 \vee X = V5$, where $V1, V2, V3, V4, V5$ represent all the possible discrete values, ensuring that all five flows are activated together regardless of which value X takes. The conditions are expanded for continuous attributes by setting the range to contain the entire possible range of values. For example, if the attribute X is defined within the $[0, 100]$ range, each of the five flows will be associated with this entire range. This setup guarantees that any value of X within the specified range will activate all five outgoing flows concurrently from the OR gateway.

Additionally, we introduced 20% noise into the data genera-

tors **EQ**, **UB**, **ND**, **ED**, and **CC1**, resulting in scenarios where some cases did not satisfy any of the predefined conditions. This setup produced 20 datasets: 15 based on the pure patterns and 5 with the added noise. The attributes used in the conditions were generated as event attributes, i.e., dynamically updated by the activities preceding the corresponding gateway.

VI. THREATS TO VALIDITY.

(1) *Internal validity*: the experiments rely on 150 synthetic datasets and 3 real-life logs. Results may vary with different datasets. We selected logs and data patterns with varying characteristics and from different domains to mitigate this limitation. (2) *Ecological validity*: We compare simulation outputs against the original log to measure how well the DAS replicates the as-is process. However, this does not assess the accuracy improvements of using data-aware models in a what-if setting, i.e., predicting performance after a change.

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